

Conference Abstract

Distribution, Population Dynamics, and Threats of the European weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (NE Germany)

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Abstract

The distribution focus of the weatherfish in Germany is clearly in the northeast. Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania is Germany's north-easternmost federal state and is located in the western part of the weatherfish's natural range. It also marks its northern border. Unfortunately, there is no available information about occurrences of the weatherfish from the time before humans fundamentally changed the landscape. Until the end of the 1970s, the documented records remained sparse and restricted to the two former duchies of Mecklenburg. However, in the 1980s, when ichthyologists started actively mapping the native fish fauna, it quickly became apparent that the species also occurs in the Western Pomeranian part of the country. In the decades that followed targeted surveys were initiated in response to the European Flora Fauna Habitat Directive. The knowledge about the distribution of the weatherfish could be successively expanded. Today, it can be said that the species occurs extensively. But this wide distribution does not mean that the species is common. Contrary to expectation, the species is caught only sporadically, and typically in low numbers.

Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania is well known for its wealth of waters. However, many of them are no longer in a truly natural state. In particular, the natural habitats assumed for the weatherfish, such as backwaters of rivers or small standing floodplain waters,

have largely disappeared. On the other hand, the cultivation of the land has produced an intricate network of melioration drainage ditches, which often serve as suitable substitute habitats for the weatherfish. Given that the total length of drainage ditches is estimated to exceed 30,000 kilometres, the theoretical habitat potential for the species may even surpass its original extent.

To explore the habitat preferences, a database with over 67000 fish records with information on the type of water body was analysed. The results show that the frequency of weatherfish records is many times higher in the drainage ditches than in any other habitat type. Even in the types of water that are considered typical natural habitats the species is found much less frequently. Other fish species are more frequent in the drainage ditches, and many of them also occur there in much higher densities. However, none of them show such a distinct preference for this habitat type as the weatherfish.

The available database also provides information on the long-term trend of the overall population for the period 1990 - 2024. Therefore, the frequencies of weatherfish records that have occurred each year can be used. A relatively stable development over this period of time could be detected, albeit at a low level

Monitoring of selected populations began in 2008 at six initial sites, with four additional sites added by 2016. Since the initial surveys, monitoring has been conducted at three-year intervals using electrofishing in 50-meter sections. The fishings are conducted in two or more passes, allowing the current stock size of each section to be estimated using the removal method algorithms. To date, the observed populations have generally exhibited low individual densities. However, in several populations, much higher densities occurred compared to the average situation. These temporary increases were generally attributable to a rise in a single age group. This suggests that either reproduction or recruitment is highly irregular. Populations with such dynamics definitely have a higher risk of local extinction than continuously reproducing populations. Therefore, a favourable environment for a well-regulated metapopulation is essential. To improve the stability of existing populations and reduce the risks of extinction, the upstream passability of the drainage systems and also of their connecting waters should be improved or re-established.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.